

HIGH TEMPERATURE POLYMERS IN AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS

James K. Sutter
*NASA Glenn Research Center
at Lewis Field
Cleveland, OH 44135*

ABSTRACT

A review of the NASA Glenn Higher Operating Temperature Propulsion Components Project (HOTPC) on polymer matrix composites (PMCs) will be described. The summary includes research from NASA GRC in-house, university and industry's cooperative programs that are related to the design and fabrication of an access to space application

Keywords: Polymer composites, coatings, polyimide

INTRODUCTION

NASA and several DoD agencies are largely responsible for the current research on high temperature polymers in aerospace applications. While there are many fads that come and go in this research area, there is one that has remained constant—both NASA and DoD realize the tremendous impact that high temperature polymers have on aero vehicles and their engines. As an example of their teamwork, DoD and NASA sponsor an annual workshop that highlights the several US governmental agencies, university and industry research on high temperature polymers called *High Temple*. More information about this workshop can be found at <http://namis.alionscience.com>. Most of the research leading to commercial high temperature polymer products has focused on composite applications for aircraft. This paper focuses on high temperature polymers proposed for use in space propulsion applications and serves as a review for NASA project *Higher Operating Temperature Propulsion Components* (HOTPC).

In the past 10 years, research on high temperature polymers was stimulated by the need to reduce manufacturing costs of advanced aircraft airframe and propulsion components.¹ Many of these cost saving approaches focused on electron beam cured or resin transfer molded structures. Despite these efforts, PMR-15 and its second-generation variants: Avimid®, PMR-II, AFR700 comprise the largest share of the commercial high temperature polymer market. This paper will focus on research goals reducing the weight of a space propulsion component that requires a high temperature polymer composite with thermal properties equivalent to second-generation PMR polyimides. Therefore, graphite fiber PMR-II-50 polyimide composites were chosen for this application.

NASA and the United States Air Force have a need to reduce their costs in accessing space for both commercial and military purposes. The continued high costs of operating the Space Shuttle has led both organizations to propose and build several shuttle alternative vehicles. Many of these vehicles were designed around the concept that a single stage to orbit (SSTO) would

Figure 1. SS Combustor Case

require less maintenance, lower launch costs and have a lower gross take-off weight. Therefore, NASA teamed with Boeing Rocketdyne to develop lightweight propulsion components for a SSTO liquid hydrogen fueled engine. This team's goal was to reduce component weight and increase component durability. The component chosen was a combustion chamber support structure—currently made from stainless steel—whose major function is to maintain the shape of the combustion chamber so that an efficient fuel burn is possible (Figure 1).

PROJECT OVERVIEW

Boeing Rocketdyne produces a variety of space propulsion systems and very few contain polymer composites. Engineers at Boeing identified the combustion chamber support on a mid-sized liquid hydrogen fueled engine as a prime candidate for the weight reduction. This component experiences rapid heating from the hot gases inside the combustor that are hundreds of degrees Celsius per second. These heating rates provide several challenges for both the component structure and its composite materials. Structurally, the inner combustor chamber must maintain its shape for efficient combustion. Composite materials should provide the stiffness to maintain these critical dimensions by tailoring the ply structure with an appropriate core material. Absorbed moisture naturally occurs in polyimide based polymer composites. These materials will contain water, 1-2% by weight, while stored at ambient conditions. Composite structures that are rapidly heated will blister or delaminate after the first heating cycle. Further, these materials usually suffer from low interlaminar stresses such as shear.

Solving these challenges requires a multidisciplinary team of structural, material and test engineers. Moreover, this team's research and development approach required not simply building and testing the structure. Instead, a multifaceted approach was planned where a structural design team identified the components thermal and mechanical loads and then calculated the resulting deformations. While, a materials team tackled the inherent difficulties that high temperature polymer composites present under the rapid heating conditions. Figure 2 identifies these teams and a description of their contribution follows. A detailed description of the key contributions to this program is listed in the subsequent papers from our session.

Figure2. NASA-Boeing HOTPC Team

MATERIALS

PMR-II-50 polyimide is a lightly crosslinked addition curing resin that can sustain higher thermal loads than PMR-15.² PMR-II-50 imide oligomer is shown below in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Fully imidized PMR-II-50 Oligomer

Maverick Corporation (Cincinnati, Ohio) supplied this resin in a variety of monomer solid concentrations depending on the type of composites needed for testing.³ YLA Inc (Benicia, California) applied PMR-II-50 to the M40J fiber in the form of a methanolic solution. High Quality prepreg was supplied by YLA Inc. in either fabric or “Uni-tape” form. After extension materials testing, Boeing Rocketdyne chose Toray’s M40J polyacrylonitrile based carbon fiber.⁴ This fiber is unique in that it has an excellent balance of properties: high modulus and tensile strength.

Composites requiring long-term survivability at high temperatures require durable interfacial properties between the fiber and the resin. In order to improve on these properties, several research programs have focused on improving the sizing on reinforcements.⁵ Adherent Technologies (Albuquerque, New Mexico) has extensive experience provided tailored surface finishes to carbon, glass, graphite, and Kevlar®. A recent study⁶ demonstrated an effective method to characterize the surface properties of Toray’s M40J fiber. This study identifies the acid/base properties as well as the prevalent functional groups on the fiber’s surface when compared to Toray’s M60J fiber. More importantly, this study highlights the methods, such as x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), used to characterize un-sized and sized carbon fiber as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. XPS Results for Toray’s M Fibers: Desized/Sized

Moiety	M40J Sized	M40J Desized	M60J Sized	M60J Desized
%C-C	39.8	72.2	54.7	70.4
%C-O	34.4	14.7	26.7	13.2
%C-O-O	2.1	0.7	1.4	0.9
% O1s	23.7	12.5	17.2	15.3

An example of the M40J fiber surface topography, Figure 4 shows M40J as-sized from Toray, desized at Adherent Tech., and then resized or finished with a proprietary sizing which contains a unique coupling agent from Adherent Technology.

Figure 4. M40J Micrographs: (a) as received or commercial size, (b) desized, (c) resized

Tensile shear tests were run on composites fabricated from the three fiber treatments: as received, desized and resided.. These results show that the refinished fibers have a stronger and more thermally stable interface, whereas the desized fibers have the weakest and least thermally table interface. The laminates made with fibers treated with the manufacturer’s sizing are in between the other two treatments as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. In-Plane Shear strength of M40J/PMR-II-50 Composites (24-ply)

STRUCTURES

Design engineers at Boeing Rocketdyne provided the thermal and mechanical predictions for the combustor support case. Excellent correlation between predicted and measured composite deflection properties were confirmed at NASA. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) demonstrated that the current composite design would meet the engine test conditions. A normalized view of the thermal-mechanical components loads is shown in Fig. 6. Moreover, deflection load and limits of sandwich structure were assessed at Gougeon Brothers, (Midland, Michigan) and confirmed using FEA. Currently, thermal mechanical fatigue (TMF) testing is underway. Initial results will be presented.

Figure 6. Simulated Thermal-Mechanical Fatigue Cycle

Polymer composite structures that experience rapid heating may have to be stitched through the thickness. Recently, by McDonald and Chuang⁷ suggest that flexural properties of the high temperature stitched composites can withstand rapid increases in temperature. The trade-off in mechanical properties from stitched composites comes in reduce compressive properties due to the damage of resulting from the stitching as shown in Figure 7. In cases where compressive strength is not critical, the stitches can aid in the evolution of trapped moisture or residual cure or degradation byproducts.

Figure 7. Stitched high temperature PMC.

Studies by Rice et al.⁸ describe the effects that absorbed moisture can have on carbon fiber/polyimide composites. The resulting blistering is not only a problem at rapid heating rates but at heating rates considered “typical” for aero-propulsion composite components. In Table 2, the effect of heating rates on laminate blistering with and without a variety of stitch densities is shown. Note that stitching can reduce the blistering as volatiles escape through pathways created by the stitch.

Table 2. Blister Testing on Unstitched/Stitched PMCs

Stitch Density	Void Cont. %	Moisture Uptake, %	Blister Onset, °C	
			Slow	Fast
Un-stitched	2.3 ± 0.4	1.47	262	N/A
Low	5.8 ± 0.1	1.74	None	280
Medium 1	4.9 ± 1.2	1.74	None	None
Medium 2; thick yarn	4.6 ± 0.1	1.64	None	310
High	3.6 ± 0.5	1.63	None	N/A

Several organizations contributed to the final design of the combustor case. The critical design requirement was to maintain the dimensional integrity of the inner combustor chamber. To meet these criteria, a sandwich structure was proposed and FEA modeling of a metallic core and high temperature M40J/PMR-II-50 PMC face sheet satisfied the support structure requirements. Bonding these two dissimilar materials required a high temperature adhesive. Research at Wright Patterson Air Force Base (Dayton, Ohio), University of Dayton Research Institute and Boeing led to the development of very effective primers for the metallic core. Cytec’s FM680-1 adhesive satisfied both the temperature and shear properties requirements for

this sandwich structure and extensive PMC/Metallic core deflection testing at GBI. Deflection testing of flat, unconfigured cored structures is shown in Figure 8.

At this time, the metallic cored sandwich structure is the leading candidate. Therefore, Boeing and UDRI performed lap shear testing. Results from these tests are shown in Figure 9. While

the tensile values are normalized to the highest strength sample, eg. Metal-1, the tensile strengths for the M40J/PMR-II-50 at both elevated temperature and surpassed the room temperature testing after a water boil were higher than the tensile strengths for either metallic core substrate. This is a critical result for this structure because as it is rapidly heated, the out-of-plane deflections will rely on the adhesive's tensile strength.

Figure 8. M40J/PMR-II-50 cored metallic structure

Figure 9. FM680-1 Adhesive Tensile Lap Shear Strength-Normalized to highest strength

Extensive efforts to understand the high temperature composite response to rapid heating was accomplished at Southern Research Institute (SRI) The goal of this effort was to properly attach thermocouples to the M40J/PMR-II-50 composite and develop an accurate model for the surface

heating under rapid heating conditions. The furnace used to perform these rapid heating experiments is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Rapid heating Furnace at SRI

Naturally, there was an equilibrium period for the thermocouples to achieve their steady state temperature. Figure 11. shows the effect of sample position within the furnace and more importantly, the temperature differences between the front and back composite surfaces during a heating experiment.

Figure 11. Effect of specimen position within the High Heating Rate Facility at SRI

These thermal response profiles aided in the selection of composite architecture, since polyimide composites can blister while being rapidly heated. The effect of heating rate and moisture evolution for several composite ply lay-up configurations was determined and ply structure optimized based on composite residual shear strength and compressive modulus loss. Detailed description of these testing programs follows in subsequent papers.

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